

Women Entrepreneurship in India – Problems and Prospects

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Introduction

Women Entrepreneurs India provides the right tools that help in the start up and expansion of businesses, run by women entrepreneurs. We aim to create the required platform for idea exchange, business advising, entrepreneurship awareness, development, marketing support, mentorship opportunities, etc., which can help in the professional growth of the businesses. An Indian woman in the pursuit of the entrepreneurial dream. Women have always been involved in small, usually home-based businesses but this is different. We are more visible, we are more ambitious and we hear more women talking about building businesses, not just earning an income. What is driving so many women to start businesses? What challenges do they face? What helps them succeed? Does gender enter the entrepreneur’s mind at all? These were only some of the questions we had, and out of that emerged the Women’s Web Women & Entrepreneurship in India 2012 Study.

The study was conducted online between June 1st and 20th and we received responses from 114 women entrepreneurs across the country. Below are the results, which will be of interest to entrepreneurs, entrepreneurs-in-the-making, mentors, advisors, funding firms and anyone with an interest in the story of women and entrepreneurship in India.

Concept of Women entrepreneurs in India

Age & Education

A significant chunk (58%) of the entrepreneurs we surveyed had started their businesses between the ages of 20 and 30; interestingly, 25% had started up even before turning 25. It raises the possibility of at least some women starting up businesses without first holding a job, right after their education. As expected, most were either graduates or post-graduates.

Which cities are producing India's women entrepreneurs?

Bangalore leads all other cities head and shoulders in the presence of women entrepreneurs. Kolkata is the only absentee large metro (tucked away under 'others'), with all the others such as Chennai, the National Capital Region (NCR), Pune, Mumbai and Hyderabad figuring in the list.

Industry Type

As for **industry type**, Professional services, IT/ITES, Apparel/accessories and Food & Beverages are the four major sectors in which women own businesses (59% of those surveyed). The majority of women-owned businesses are **micro-enterprises or small/mid-sized businesses**, with 73% reporting a revenue of under Rs.10,00,000 (Rs. Ten lakh or One million) in the last financial year. Corresponding to this, the majority had **fewer than 5 employees** (71%).

Women starting businesses: Motivation and capital

57% of women entrepreneurs had started their businesses alone, while 35% had a co-founder and 8% were part of teams that involved more than 2 co-founders.

The opportunity to **work more creatively** and the perceived benefit of **being one's own boss** were the top reasons chosen. While work-life balance was also chosen (by 36%), that was not the biggest reason for women turning entrepreneurs, as is commonly perceived. 60% of women entrepreneurs started their business with a **capital of under Rs.1,00,000**, and personal funds and savings were used to start the business in a majority of cases. However, 30% of those surveyed stated that they had used more 1 source of funding.

Challenges, support, joys, goals

We asked women entrepreneurs to pick **their challenges**, both at the time of starting up and at present; they are not the same. **Financial and Marketing** related challenges emerge as the top pick at both times. People challenges however are stronger at present than while starting up indicating that as teams grow, so do the challenges associated with them. **Personal challenges** (bandwidth/time management) however, drastically taper off suggesting that women's confidence in their own abilities as entrepreneurs has grown with the experience.

As for support in their entrepreneurial journey, besides friends and family (the top choices), the growing importance of the entrepreneurial community is reflected in the fact that 26% mentioned other entrepreneurs and entrepreneur groups. 23% also mentioned mentors and advisors. Perhaps my personal favourite among all the charts that emerged from this survey is the one below. When asked the biggest benefit they had derived from starting up their businesses, this is what women had to say.

The majority chose **growth and profitability related goals** (81 and 53% respectively). This may not directly answer the question of whether women entrepreneurs want to scale up their businesses or not, but it does indicate that women's businesses are not just hobbies or life style businesses, as sometimes alleged. We received a total of 107 responses on **what would help them achieve these goals**, and the ones listed most often were recruiting skilled people (21%) and funding or financial support (20%).

Gender & Entrepreneurship

We asked our respondents to consider the question of entrepreneurship through the prism of gender. What did they believe? In short: Yes, it is harder to start a business if you are a woman (55%). Yes, knowing other women who run businesses is a big support (73%). Yes, being a woman impacts decisions on how large/fast the business should grow (52%). On the question of **whether a female mentor was better** for women entrepreneurs, opinion was more divided. The Women’s Web Women & Entrepreneurship in India 2012 Study has been boundaries.

How to Develop Women Entrepreneurship

A Right efforts on from all areas are required in the development of women entrepreneurs and their greater participation in the entrepreneurial activities. Following efforts can be taken into account for effective development of women entrepreneurs.

- Consider women as specific target group for all developmental programmers.
- Better educational facilities and schemes should be extended to women folk from government part.
- Adequate training programmed on management skills to be provided to women community.
- Encourage women’s participation in decision-making.
- Vocational training to be extended to women community that enables them to understand the production process and production management.
- Skill development to be done in women’s polytechnics and industrial training institutes. Skills are put to work in training-cum-production workshops.
- Training on professional competence and leadership skill to be extended to women entrepreneurs.
- Training and counseling on a large scale of existing women entrepreneurs to remove psychological causes like lack of self-confidence and fear of success.
- Counseling through the aid of committed NGOs, psychologists, managerial experts and technical personnel should be provided to existing and emerging women entrepreneurs.
- Continuous monitoring and improvement of training programmers.
- Activities in which women are trained should focus on their marketability and profitability.
- Making provision of marketing and sales assistance from government part.
- To encourage more passive women entrepreneurs the Women training programmed should be organized that taught to recognize her own psychological needs and express them.

Advantages of Female entrepreneurship

- **Social Networking** Let’s face it-women are natural networkers. They love to talk, mingle, and rub elbows. This is the very reason why husbands rarely ever manage the social calendar. In today’s business environment, mastering social media is mandatory, and the ladies absolutely have a leg up.
- **Intuition** They call it “women’s intuition” for a reason. Women in general can size up another person much faster than her male counterpart. In today’s ultra-fast paced business environment, you need the ability to quickly identify the allies and the enemies. Regardless if you are a male or female, you need to trust your gut.
- **Pain Tolerance** Okay, initially I would have said this is irrelevant. But after watching my children be born, there is no question that my wife can handle a lot more pain than I can. And I am not just talking physical pain, I mean emotional, too (have you seen how tough children can be on their mothers?). In business, there are a lot of painful moments. Women definitely have an advantage in this area.

- **Multi-tasking** Women are known for juggling many tasks at the same time and still being able to produce excellent results. Conversely, the guys are masters at focusing on one thing. Still, the advantage in today's distracting environment goes to women.
- **Patience** Women inherently seem to have more patience. And in today's business environment, patience is key. Aggressive business strategies are not paying off like they once did. Slow and steady wins the race in this category.
- **Listening** A friend of mine went to buy a new bed at a small bedding store owned by a husband and wife team. The female owner approaches my friend and asked all kinds of questions about why they needed a new bed, if they could fix their old bed, what else they were considering, etc. She asked questions and listened closely. She clearly showed that she cared about helping to meet their needs. My friend was moments away from buying any bed that she recommended. But just then, the frustrated husband on the sales team ran up and said "let me handle this." Then he just tried to hard close the sale. He was pushy, telling them what he recommended and what they had to have. Guess what? The sale was lost the second he began speaking! They walked out. I am sure he blamed her, but it was him. The key is to ask questions and really listen. Quite frankly, any great sales person knows this, man or woman, it just seems that the ladies are naturally better at doing it.

A Case study success female entrepreneurship in India

Women have come a long way from just being a homemaker. Narendra Modi's start up friendly environment in the country has proved to be a blessing for female entrepreneurs and instrumental and instrumental in fighting gender stereotyping in the business community.

Indu Jain

Indu Jain belongs to the Sahu Jain family and is the current chairperson of India's largest media group, Bennett, Coleman & Co. Ltd., which owns the Times of India and other large newspapers. She is widowed with two sons. Indu Jain is known by many different identities such as that of a spiritualist, humanist, entrepreneur, an aficionado of culture and the arts, an educationalist but her most prominent and eminent role has been that of Chairman. Ms Jain was awarded the Padma Bhushan by the Government Of India in January 2016. She is also the guiding force behind The Oneness Forum, formally launched by the President of India in 2003. The Forum recently awarded the Mahatma-Mahavira Awards to outstanding individuals from all of walks of life and is involved in several activities that seek to bring, and highlight, a sense of Oneness in the world.

Kiran Mazumdar Shaw

She is the founder Chairman and Managing Director (CMD) of Biocon Limited. Born in Bangalore, Shaw completed her Bachelors in Zoology from Mount Carmel College, Bangalore University. She later did her post-graduation in Malting and Brewing from Ballarat College, Melbourne University. She worked as a trainee brewer in Carlton and United Breweries, Melbourne and as a trainee maltster at Barrett Brothers and Burston, Australia. She started Biocon in 1978 and spearheaded its evolution from an industrial enzymes manufacturing company to a fully integrated bio-pharmaceutical company. Today Biocon under Shaw's leadership has established itself as a leading player in biomedicine research with a focus on diabetes and oncology. Kiran is also a member of the board of governors of the prestigious Indian School of Business and Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad. Kiran received the padma shri (1989) and padma Bhushan (2005) from the government of India.

Indra Nooyi

The most well-known face amongst Indian women entrepreneurs -Indra Nooyi is the CFO and President of PepsiCo. With a Masters Degree in Public Management from Yale University and Masters in Finance and Marketing from IIM, Kolkata, Nooyi held several senior positions at Motorola and Asea Brown Boveri before joining PepsiCo. Born in Chennai, Indra did her Bachelor's in Science from Madras Christian College in 1974. Beginning her career in India, Nooyi held product manager positions at Johnson & Johnson and textile firm Mettur Beardsell. Nooyi joined PepsiCo in 1994 and was named president and CFO in 2001. She has been conferred with prestigious Padma Bhushan for her business achievements and being an inspiration to India's corporate leadership. Her strong acumen for business has helped the company garner as much as 30 billion dollars worth of crucial deals within the last couple of years.

Vandana Luthra

VLCC, a beauty and wellness giant has its presence in 11 countries across Asia, Africa and the GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council) and the credit goes to Vandana Luthra. Initially, a homemaker, Vandana started her journey in 1989 when the first of her two daughters was only 3 years-old. Born in Kolkata, West Bengal, this beauty expert got herself well versed with beauty, fitness, food and nutrition and skin care when she pursued higher education in Germany, UK and France, after completing a professional course from the Polytechnic for Women in New Delhi. She was awarded the Padma Shri in 2013 for her contribution. and in 2015, she was listed as the 33rd most powerful woman in business in India by Fortune India.

Naina Lal Kidwai

Naina has a Bachelor's degree in Economics from Delhi university and an MBA from Harvard Business school. In fact, Kidwai was the first Indian woman to graduate from Harvard Business School. From being Head of Investment Banking at ANZ Grindlays during 1982-1994 to Vice Chairman JM Morgan Stanley, Naina Lal Kidwai is one of the most successful and famous Indian businesswomen of today. She is currently Country Head and Group General Manager HSBC Group India. Apart from working at HSBC, Kidwai has also held other eminent positions such as that of Global Advisor, Harvard Business School, non-executive director at Nestle SA and as a member of Governing Board NCAER, Auditor General of India and several other positions. Indian government conferred Padma Shri award on Naina for her contributions in the field of Trade and Industry.

Chanda Kochhar

She is currently the MD & CEO of India's largest private bank ICICI Bank. Rajasthan born Chanda got Masters Degree in Management Studies from Jamnalal Bajaj Institute of Management Studies, Mumbai. She received the Wockhardt Gold Medal for Excellence in Management Studies as well as the J. N. Bose Gold Medal in Cost Accountancy. Chanda Kochhar is married to Deepak Kochhar, a wind energy entrepreneur and her Business schoolmate. Under Kochhar's leadership, ICICI Bank won the "Best Retail Bank in India" award in 2001, 2003, 2004 and 2005 and "Excellence in Retail Banking Award" in 2002; both awards were given by The Asian Banker. Kochhar personally was awarded "Retail Banker of the Year 2004 (Asia-Pacific region)" by the Asian Banker, "Business Woman of the Year 2005" by The Economic Times and "Rising Star Award" for Global Awards 2006 by Retail Banker International.

Ekta Kapoor

The woman who changed the face of Indian television – Love them or hate them, you just cannot ignore Balaji serials and Ekta Kapoor is the woman who single-handedly founded and made Balaji Telefilms the household name it is today. This baby-faced teenager, who once dreamed of marrying and settling down just like any other woman in India, is the creative head of Balaji Telefilms and counted as one of the top 10 women entrepreneurs of today. Her production house has many hit serials to its credit – ‘Kyunki Saas Bhi Kabhi Bahu Thi’, ‘Kahani Ghar Ghar Ki’ and many others, making her the Queen Bee of the Indian soap opera scene. She has won the Hall of Fame award at the 6th Indian Telly Awards during 2006 for her contribution to the Indian television industry. Known to be fiercely protective of her company and brand, Ekta is also very professional and has strong business acumen.

Suchi Mukherjee

Limeroad was started in 2012 by Suchi along with Manish Saksena, Ankush Mehra and Prashant Malik. The company has raised a funding of \$20 Million from Lightspeed venture partners, Matrix partners and Tiger Global. Suchi post graduated from London School of Economics and graduated from St. Stephen’s College, Delhi. In his life Suchi received many awards and recognition like K.C. Nag Economics Prize for best student in Economics, George K. George Memorial Scholarship for overall contribution, all at St. Stephen’s College, Delhi University, Cambridge Commonwealth Trust, Scholarship & Fellowship, and Chadburn Scholarship for merit, both at Cambridge University and British Chevening Scholarship, at the London School of Economics. Suchi was selected as 1 of 15 women worldwide ‘Rising Talents, high potential leaders under 40. Suchi is an ex-ebay, Skype and Gumtree.

Richa Kar

Richa is the founder of online lingerie store Zivame , she grew up in Jamshedpur and completed her engineering from BITS Pilani (2002) and after having worked briefly in the IT industry she acquired Masters’ degree from Narsee Monji Institute of Management Studies in 2007, and worked with a retailer and global technology company before starting Zivame.com. Zivame is probably the first in the online lingerie space in India and has played a role in educating women across the country about intimate wear and shaping consumer behaviour.

Aditi Gupta

One the most common taboos is Menstruation, but with time, it is getting the attention that is needed for the society to accept the fact and talk openly about it. One such initiative has been taken by Aditi Gupta. In 2012, she co-founded Menstrupedia with Tuhin Paul, a crowdfunded initiative. The company provides a resourceful guide about menstruation which helps women to stay healthy and active during their menstruation. Aditi is a post-graduate in New Media Design from National Institute of Design, and graduated in Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering. Aditi first got the idea for Menstrupedia while doing her thesis on the very subject for her post graduation at NID (National Institute of Design). Aditi was born and brought up in Garhwa, a small town in Jharkhand.

Problems of Women Entrepreneurship in India

A very long time business was considered a male-dominated sphere. Women did not have any access to the business. There was not the slightest possibility for a woman to introduce herself with a start-up or establish her own business some gender stereotypes appeared to be too deeply rooted

to disappear quickly. Though we can see a number of women entrepreneurs, fewer women still manage to succeed in their business.

Here you find some of the most common challenges women entrepreneurs face on every step. So, let's get known with problems of women entrepreneurship, which are a nasty burden for each woman in business. Let's explore the main factors which build barriers for women's full integration in that men-possessed sphere.

A woman full of enthusiasm, new ideas, and readiness to fulfil her plans and ideas, is about to start her new business. She has considered everything connected with the risks, finances and the remaining stuff. The chance of failure is little. Everything is clearly taken into account. A woman is passionate to follow her dream and takes the first necessary steps to fulfil her plans. However, things don't go their logical way. What's wrong? The action plan doesn't work! From the very beginning of establishing her business, the woman starts facing some barriers. Oh, wait: is there anything she didn't take into consideration? Where this kind of barriers come from? Maybe all these are just because she's a woman?

Media shouts about gender equality as loud as it can. “Women, like men, can try themselves in all the spheres,” they say. The facts, however, come to prove the opposite. Very often women in business and social entrepreneurs face a number of challenges because of some gender stereotypes existing today.

Having a hard time to be you

Many women in the business face this problem. There is a widely ruling stereotype that a real leader should look manly. Many women in business take this idea for granted and tend to look like their male counterparts.

In this way, they think their ideas would look more convincing and trustworthy. We can witness the example of such like behavior during many board meetings where women dress men style suits trying to look more masculine. This is a typical representation of deeply rooted stereotype and what's more upsetting is that women themselves become the victims of the stereotype without realizing it.

Women, always remember never lose your personality and be yourself regardless how the opposite sex perceives it. Your skills and talents have nothing in common with your sex, appearance, and behavior. Make everybody finally get it.

Funding gets difficult if you are a woman

Many women social entrepreneurs are constantly complaining about the fact that getting funding is much more difficult for women than for men. They are pretty sure men are more inclined to fund those people who belonged to the same gender as they are. This can become a real challenge for a woman. It's essential to state that the majority of venture capitalists are males.

Confidence, confidence and once again confidence needed

There is no way to a successful women entrepreneurship if there is a lack of confidence. Society likes to give people roles and is always strict towards those who deny following their roles. However, hold on for a second, ladies: is that really what you want? Never be humble to the place and role the society suggests you. If you'll planning to fly high and reach never achievements in business then, you'll also have to be ready to become Johnathan Livingston Seagull.

Lack of strength to admit your own achievements

Many girls and women come from the societies where the role of a woman is highly underestimated. This can be a reason for different cultural values ruling in the society. This kind of approach towards women affects women during their life and on their further actions. Women raised in such environment always lack the ability to appreciate the true value of their efforts and input in the business. Those factors very often create a huge barrier for a woman to succeed as an entrepreneur and have her deserved a place in business. Even if they somehow manage to overcome the barrier and enter the world of business, they still avoid of speaking their own accomplishments.

Speaking of their achievements, very often tend to use the word “we” instead of “I”. Well speaking of the second person is sometimes very efficient for team building, however very often it is viewed as an underestimation of your old powers. Still, if you really think that you deserve appreciation, then don't be afraid to state it and draw everybody's attention to it. Always remember nobody will appreciate your job until you don't do it yourself. Confidence is the key to success so keep it always with you.

Still finding time for family

A woman entrepreneur becomes a real hero when she combines two extremely responsible jobs: being a mommy and also being a successful business lady. It's out of suspicion that the task of women while being engaged in the job and at the same time taking care of the baby is much more difficult than that of a man. Moreover, in many societies, the main duty of women is considered taking care of the babies so, it's not acceptable for a woman to have another job than being a full-time mommy. If a woman is married she may face even a disapproval of husband. This will put women a step further from business activities.

Living in a male-dominated society

Living in a society where a role of a woman is underestimated and the responsibilities of women are limited, brings another challenge for a woman to become an entrepreneur. Woman will have same rights and responsibilities as men, the perception towards women at workplace will definitely differ from the perception towards men. Men will have higher opportunities to be promoted even though a woman will be more skilful and talented.

Education

We're coming across with a question why the number of women entrepreneurs is considerably fewer than the number of male entrepreneurs in less developed societies. Well, one of the key factors influencing it is the lack of education among women. In many societies, women don't have access to getting a proper education. They are not aware of business technology and marketing.

Conclusion

Women entrepreneur is a person who accepts challenging role to meet her personal need and become economically independent. There are economical, social, religious, cultural and other factors existing in the society which responsible for the emergency of the entrepreneurs. “Women entrepreneur refers equally to someone who has started a one women business to someone who is a principal in family business or partnership or to someone who is shareholder in a public company which she runs”. The Government of India has defined a women entrepreneur is ” an enterprise owned and controlled by a women having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least 51% of the employment generated in the enterprise to women”.